

Analysis of Factors that Contribute to Unsuccessful Completion of Construction Projects in Public Learning Institutions: The Case of Baringo County, Kenya

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ABSTRACT

The proportion of construction works in public learning institutions in Kenya that are unsuccessfully completed is 30 percent. A construction project is unsuccessfully completed if it suffers time and cost overruns and is of poor quality. This study aims to determine how some known factors contribute to the unsuccessful completion of works in public learning institutes in Baringo County. Multistage random sampling was applied. The data was qualitative and was collected through a self-administered questionnaire-based survey and analyzed by descriptive analysis and multivariate regression. The level of covariance of the three dependent variables (timeliness, quality, and cost of works) was 0.000. Quality and timeliness of works had a weak but statistically significant negative correlation (-0.333). Cost and quality had a moderately positive correlation (0.503). All parameters demonstrated good capacity to explain variations of all three dependent variables with unstandardized beta coefficients of 0.250, except in the circumstances outlined below. Regarding the relationship between cost and quality when the project is faced with financing challenges, the t value was -0.499, which is outside the area of acceptance at a 95 confidence level. The observed power was 0.076, and the level of significance was 0.624. Regarding the relationship between cost and timeliness of works when the project is faced with procurement challenges, the significance value was 0.176 and the t value was 1.084. Regarding the relationship between quality and cost of works when the project is faced with planning challenges, the t statistic measured 0.547, the significance statistic was 0.591, and the observed explanatory power was 0.081. All the above statistics fell outside the margin of acceptance. Unsuccessful completion of construction works is rampant in Kenya's public learning institutions because quality maximization, cost minimization, and timeliness of works cannot be attained concurrently. To maximize quality, the financing agent (NG-CDF) must forego cost minimization. The procurement team must forego cost minimization to realize timeliness. The planning team must forego quality maximization to minimize costs. It is necessary to evaluate the same research questions on a wider scale.

Keywords: Cost minimization; quality maximization; timeliness of works; unsuccessful completion

1.0 INTRODUCTION

One of the greatest challenges facing the education sector in the whole world is how to ensure the provision of adequate teaching and learning infrastructure of the right quality and at the right time (Berawi et al., 2021; Shenhar et al., 2002). This problem has been widely associated with inadequate funding brought about by insufficient budgetary allocations by the concerned state agencies (Swan and Khalfan, 2007). In the United Kingdom, for example, many decades of budgetary shortfalls resulted in a scenario where much of the public school teaching and learning infrastructure in England was too old and in a state considered not suitable for proper education (Reichstein et al., 2005; Korczynski, 1996; Ambrosio-Albala, 2023). The Blair administration solved this problem by putting into place a revolutionary public-private partnership arrangement that mobilized private capital to fund massive construction projects in public schools (Latham, 1994). In the United States of America, public school infrastructure provision has suffered chronic federal and state underfunding for many decades, and to date, it has remained difficult to work out an amicable solution that would be satisfactory to both levels of government (Murray et al., 2002; Swan and Khalfan, 2007).

In South Africa, the provision of teaching and learning infrastructure has been hampered by a national government policy that requires the management boards of public schools in poor communities to charge no fees (DOE, 2009). Whereas such a policy has enabled many South African children from poor families to stay in school, it has brought two conflicting effects: school populations have arisen amidst the inability of the school management boards to either expand facilities or maintain existing facilities (DOE, 2009). In Kenya, the institution of the National Government Constituency Development Fund has had both good and bad consequences (Muchung'u, 2012). Many researchers agree that the NG-CDF provides an efficient and well-endowed fund for ensuring the provision of teaching and learning infrastructure in public learning institutions (Saisi et al., 2015; Gwayo et al., 2014; GoK, 2013; GoK, 2015). To this extent, Kenya has been able to find a legal and institutional solution to a global problem that many countries are struggling to deal with (De Luca et al., 2021; Dimitriou et al., 2020; Kikwasi, 2012; Talukhaba, 1999).

However, despite a fairly well-structured funding mechanism, there are too many abandoned and delayed construction works in Kenya's public learning institutions (Gwayo et al., 2014; Muchungu, 2012; Saisi et al., 2015). There are also reports of poor quality buildings and exorbitant construction costs (Saisi et al., 2015). The economic losses suffered by Kenya as a country and the inconveniences experienced by the education sector due to the unsuccessful completion of construction projects are huge. Up to 30 percent of construction projects in public learning institutions in Kenya are completed but in a manner considered unsuccessful by the clients. Baringo County, like many counties in Kenya, is adversely affected by this problem. Challenges in the four key management issues in public construction projects (public financing, public procurement, public works management, and public project planning) are believed to contribute to the unsuccessful completion of construction works. The study was, therefore, necessary to unearth the role these four factors play individually and collectively in causing the unsuccessful completion of construction projects. The objectives of the study included determining how public financing, procurement, works management, and project planning challenges contribute to the unsuccessful completion of construction projects in public learning institutions in Baringo County, Kenya.

Much research has gone into the evaluation of the impacts of single variables such as financing and procurement on the successful completion of construction works in the public learning space (Saisi et al., 2015; Muchungu, 2012; Gwayo et al., 2014; Talukhaba, 1999). Yet, it remains unknown why, despite the availability of project funding, as found by Saisi et al. (2015) and Talukhaba (1999), the unsuccessful completion of projects is still common. This study used multivariate analysis to establish if any new insights might be exposed, which have evaded researchers focusing on the Kenyan scenario.

2.0 METHODOLOGY

2.1 An Overview

The study was conducted between May 10th and June 29th, 2023, in all six sub-counties of Baringo County, Kenya. All public learning institutions within Baringo County formed the target population. Baringo County is located in the former Rift Valley Province of Kenya. Its administrative headquarters are in Kabarnet town. It has a population of 666,763 people (KNBS, 2019). Baringo County borders Turkana County to the North and North East, Samburu and Laikipia Counties to the East, Nakuru County to the South, Kericho, and Uasin Gishu Counties to the South West, Elgeyo Marakwet County to the West, West Pokot County to the North West. The map of Baringo County is enclosed below in Figure 1. Baringo County was chosen for the study due to persistent reports by various national government regulatory agencies, including the Controller and Auditor General and the National Government Constituency Development Fund Board, on the prevalence of stalled, abandoned, and delayed construction projects in its public learning institutions (GoK, 2016).

Figure 1: Map of Kenya with Baringo County marked red

Source: Kenya National Cartographer, June 2023

2.2 Quantitative Design and Sample Size Determination

The study employed a cross-sectional design that involved key players in construction works in the education sector in Baringo County (Wamwere-Njoroge et al., 2021). These included NG-CDF managers, public works engineers, county directors of education, heads of public learning institutions, construction project management committee (PMC) chairpersons, and private contractors presently involved in construction works in public learning institutions. The sample size of heads of institutions and PMC chairpersons was determined using a formal sample size determination approach (John & Sam, 2009). The sample size was calculated using the sample size determination formula of Krejcie and Morgan (1970), followed by an adjustment of the naive sample size in line with the assumptions of Wamwere-Njoroge et al. (2021).

The adjusted sample size of 953 subjects was evenly distributed among the 6 sub-counties of Baringo County (Baringo East, Baringo North, Baringo Central, Baringo South, Eldama Ravine, and Mogotio). A sample frame involving all public learning institutions was established for the purposes described above. A multistage random sampling technique was then used to identify the actual institutions to be surveyed. Because only five public colleges exist in Baringo County, all colleges were involved in the study. The first step involved selecting at least 52 primary schools and 27 secondary schools from each sub-county for involvement in the study. A random sample of 312 primary schools and 162 secondary schools was drawn from 5 of the 6 sub-counties without replacement. The sixth sub-county was used for the replacement of any sub-county whose actual number of schools was less than the assigned share (52 primary and 27 secondary) or whose schools either declined to participate or were unable to participate due to insecurity or natural disasters such as flooding. Flooding and insecurity are common in certain parts of Baringo County. The main inclusion criterion (Wamwere-Njoroge, 2021) was being a public learning institution currently or recently involved in a construction project. Each school and college was to provide two respondents: the head of the institution and the PMC chairperson.

2.3 Qualitative Design

Key informants at the sub-county and county levels were selected based on the role their departments played in the facilitation, supervision, and audit of construction works in public learning institutions (John & Sam, 2009). A structured, open-ended interview schedule was sent to the officers to fill out at their convenience (Wamwere-Njoroge et al., 2021). This approach was necessary to enable the officers to complete the interview schedule at the appropriate time, allow them to cross-check information, and provide the relevant details. Each of the government officials and four of the six selected contractors filled out the interview schedule and submitted it to the researcher for analysis. The other two contractors declined to participate in the study.

2.4 Data Collection

Data was collected from various players in the education sector using multiple tools, including questionnaires, structured interview schedules, and observation checklists (Wamwere-Njoroge, 2021). These tools were pretested before being put to use (Muchungu, 2012; Kikwasi, 2012; Gwayo et al., 2014). The researcher used one trained and closely supervised enumerator per sub-county to assist in data collection (Wamwere-Njoroge, 2021). Enumerators were recruited competitively and trained on the research instruments (Talukhaba, 1999). Each enumerator was assigned a randomly selected sub-county (Saisi et al., 2015). If an enumerator landed in their home sub-county, a swap was done. Questionnaires and interview schedules collected background information on gender, age bracket, education, and

works experience (Wamwere-Njoroge, 2021). Likert scale items using a 5-point scale-very greatly (4), greatly (3), moderately (2), a little (1), and not at all (0)-were included in all the research instruments to obtain perceptions on the effect of public financing, public procurement, public works management, and public project planning challenges on the cost, quality, and timeliness of construction works in public learning institutions to assist in data collection (Wamwere-Njoroge, 2021).

2.5 Data Management and Analysis

The data was cleaned by correcting coding and numbering errors before being analyzed and exported to SPSS statistical software version 29 for analysis (Wamwere-Njoroge, 2021). Initial descriptive statistics (John and Sam, 2009) and linear multivariate regression (Shenhar et al., 2002) results on each questionnaire item were done to determine trends and identify items that required further cleaning (Wamwere-Njoroge, 2021). The regression model had three dependent and four independent variables (Pokhariyal, 2019). The dependent variables included the timeliness of construction works, the cost of construction works, and the quality of construction works in public learning institutions. The independent variables included public financing challenges, public procurement challenges, public works management challenges, and public project planning challenges. The model appeared as follows (Shenhar et al., 2002):

$$Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \varepsilon$$

Where Y_i represents the dependent variables, which were the mean scores for the construction project success indicators cost, quality, and timeliness, respectively, as reported by the respondents. The independent variables X_1 , X_2 , X_3 , and X_4 represent the mean score for the influence of X_1 -challenges in public construction project financing; X_2 -challenges in public construction project procurement; X_3 -challenges in public works management; and X_4 -challenges in public project planning, respectively. Each β_0 represents the intercept coefficient for the particular regression equation; β_1 , β_2 , β_3 , and β_4 represent the explanatory coefficients for the four respective independent variables. In each case, ε represents the error term of the regression function. Qualitative information from the key informants was organized into concepts, which were interpreted to inform the findings (Wamwere-Njoroge et al., 2021).

3.0 RESULTS

Data collection was conducted through a self-administered questionnaire-based survey (John and Sam, 2009). Checklists were used to gather additional data for triangulation purposes. Both quantitative and qualitative techniques were employed in data collection to enable triangulation and enrich information on the subject under investigation (Wamwere-Njoroge et al., 2021). A structured questionnaire was administered to a sample of 953 prospective respondents in the education sector in Baringo. The overall response rate was 63.9 percent. The institution-based respondents interviewed included the school and college heads and the construction project management committee (PMC) chairpersons. To supplement and triangulate the information collected from the school-based respondents, key informant interviews with other government officials and private school building contractors were conducted (Wamwere-Njoroge et al., 2021). Four contractors currently engaged in public school and college construction works were interviewed. Key informant government officials included each of the six NG-CDF fund managers, the six sub-county public works engineers, the county director of primary and secondary education, and the county director of technical

education. Self-administered interview schedules were sent to the officers and contractors, and a period of two weeks was allowed for them to read, cross-check information, and fill in the interview schedules before returning them to the researcher (Wamwere-Njoroge et al., 2021).

As shown in Table 1 below, the pool of respondents had more males than females. Males comprised 64 percent of all valid responses, while females made up the remaining 36 percent. Since this study involved mostly personnel in management positions in government agencies, the gender distribution reveals that there is a gender disparity in favor of males in management positions in the education sector in Baringo County. Less than 4 percent of the respondents were under 30 years of age. Another 7 percent were aged between 30 and 35 years. About a fifth of the respondents were aged between 36 and 40 years. Some 70 percent of the respondents were over 40 years of age. Those aged between 41 and 45 years of age comprised 30 percent of the respondents. Another 40 percent of the respondents were over 45 years old. This distribution is expected since most people in management positions in Kenya are senior public servants who have served for at least 15 years. As shown in Table 1, about 54 percent of the respondents had been in their respective positions for less than 5 years. Another 26 percent had served for 5 to 10 years. Only 20 percent of the respondents had held their respective positions of responsibility for over 10 years. This result is not surprising because most people ascend to management levels in public service after working for nearly 20 years. This means that they can hardly serve for 15 years before they are due to retire from public service.

It is assumed one acquires public construction project management experience by actually being in the relevant office and running projects. The fact that over 50 percent of the respondents had been in their positions of responsibility for less than five years could imply that a lack of experience by project management teams is responsible for the unsuccessful completion of construction projects in public learning institutions. This finding is a corroboration of opinions expressed by other workers (Bayliss et al., 2004; Anvuur and Kumaraswamy, 2007; Odeh and Battaineh, 2002; Maloney, 2000). As shown in Table 1, over 98 percent of respondents had a postgraduate qualification, a first degree, or some diploma. Even though many primary school heads first joined the teaching profession as P1 holders, an educational qualification below a diploma, by the time they were appointed to institutional management positions, they generally had upgraded their qualifications to at least a diploma. One-fifth of the respondents had a diploma. Another 54 percent had a first degree. About a quarter had postgraduate qualifications. The general educational qualifications of the respondents were quite high. Lack of education among the parties concerned, therefore, cannot be an explanation for the fact that 30 percent of construction projects in Baringo County are unsuccessfully completed.

Table 1: Demographics of the Respondents

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Female	383	64.5
	Male	211	35.5
Age	Below 30 Years	4	0.7
	30-35 Years	16	2.7
	36-40 Years	119	20.1
	41-45 Years	192	32.4
	Above 45 Years	263	44.1
Works experience	Less than 5 Years	320	53.7
	5-10 Years	154	26.0
	11-15 Years	56	9.5
	Over 15 Years	64	10.8
Education level	Diploma in Education	115	19.3
	Non-Educational Diploma	4	0.8
	Degree in Education	305	51.4
	Other Degrees	14	2.3
	Post-graduate Degree	147	24.7
	Others	9	1.5

3.1 Regression Results

Model Fitness Test

Fitness tests were done for each of the three dependent variables: timeliness of construction works, quality of construction works, and cost of construction works in public learning institutions. As shown in Table 2 below, both sums of squares and mean squares for lack of fit for all three dependent variables were very low (0.000). The sum of squares and mean squares for pure error were equally low (0.000). This is an indication of a good fit for each of the dependent variables. Any biases in the study could therefore not be attributed to a poor choice of dependent variables.

Table 2: The Model Fitness Test Matrix

Dependent Variable	Source	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	Partial Eta Squared
Timeliness of construction works in public learning institutions	Lack of Fit	.000	.000	1.000
	Pure Error	.000	.000	
Quality of construction products in public learning institutions	Lack of Fit	.000	.000	1.000
	Pure Error	.000	.000	
Cost of construction works in public learning institutions	Lack of Fit	.000	.000	1.000
	Pure Error	.000	.000	

3.2 Residual Sum of Squares Analysis

The magnitude of any residuals in multivariate regression analysis is important, as it indicates whether the independent variables chosen by the researcher can exhaustively explain variations in the value of the dependent variable. A good choice of independent variables results in the lowest value of residuals. As shown in Table 3 below, in this study, the sum of squares for residuals for all three regression equations is minimal (0.000). This implies that the choice of independent variables for the regression model is good. No independent

variable that could be used in this multivariate linear regression model has been left out (Hoskisson et al., 1999).

Equally important is the level of covariance between pairs of the three dependent variables. There are three possible combinations of the three variables: timeliness versus quality, timeliness versus cost, and cost versus quality. In all circumstances, the level of covariance was very low (0.000). The degree of covariance measures the probability that the paired dependent variables measure the same parameter. If the degree of covariance is high, then the dependent variables measure the same parameter and should either be merged or one of them dropped in favor of the other (Pokhariyal, 2019).

Table 3 below also shows the level of correlation between the three pairs of dependent variables. The cost and timeliness of construction works have a strong positive correlation (0.647). A construction project at a public learning institution that takes a long time to complete will usually cost more. This resonates with the findings of many authors (Eriksson, 2008; Collins and Baccarini, 2004; Chua et al., 1999; Cheung et al., 2003), who argued that this positive correlation is attributable to the fact that public construction works engineers focus on short-term individual sub-optimization rather than the long-term performance of the project management team. This compromises project cost performance and results in unwarranted time overruns. Anvuur and Kumaraswamy (2007) called for increased cooperation between public construction project managers (the public works engineer) and the other parties in the project management committee to promote the successful delivery of the objectives of the project.

Quality and timeliness have a weak but statistically significant negative correlation at a 95 percent level of confidence (-0.333). The longer a construction project at a public learning institution takes to complete, the lower the quality of the works. This reaffirms the findings of some authors on the relationship between timeliness and quality in public construction projects (Dubois and Gadde, 2002; Crawley and Aho, 1999; Bresnen and Marshall, 2000). Both Andi and Minato (2003) and Korczynski (1996) found that prolonged construction project durations resulted in reduced quality of the final product. They blamed it on a lack of inclusivity during the procurement process. Writing on the same subject, Eriksson and Laan (2007) argued that the exclusion of the contractor from the design process resulted in a divorce between design and construction works, with the consequence that projects took longer than planned and resulted in buildings of poor quality. Adding their voice to the debate on the relationship between quality and timeliness, Andi and Minato (2003) proposed that to reduce the risk of defective, unbuildable designs, which invariably resulted in time overruns and poor product quality, there should be increased coordination between the designer and contractor. This position has also been echoed by other writers (Tam, 2000; Tam et al., 2006; Tam and Tam, 2008; Murray et al., 2002).

Cost and quality have a moderately positive correlation (0.503). If the quality of the final product is high, construction project clients in public learning institutions must be prepared to spend large sums of money. Tam et al. (2006) found that construction project planners tend to avoid environmental compliance and public health and safety obligations to prevent cost overruns. Such decisions have consequences for the quality of both the process and the final product (Koehn and Datta, 2003; Maloney, 2002). In a regime where strict environmental and public health and safety laws exist, a construction project that circumvents the law might suffer litigation and penalties, resulting in delays and cost overruns (Koehn and Datta, 2003).

Table 3: Residual sum of Squares Matrix

		Timeliness of construction works in public learning institutions	Quality of construction products in public learning institutions	Cost of construction works in public learning institutions
Sum-of-Squares and Cross-Products	Timeliness of construction works in public learning institutions	.000	.000	.000
	Quality of construction products in public learning institutions	.000	.000	.000
	Cost of construction works in public learning institutions	.000	.000	.000
Covariance	Timeliness of construction works in public learning institutions	.000	.000	.000
	Quality of construction products in public learning institutions	.000	.000	.000
	Cost of construction works in public learning institutions	.000	.000	.000
Correlation	Timeliness of construction works in public learning institutions	1.000	-.333	.647
	Quality of construction products in public learning institutions	-.333	1.000	.503
	Cost of construction works in public learning institutions	.647	.503	1.000

3.3 Regression Parameter Estimates.

A total of 12 parameters were analyzed for their influence on the three dependent variables. The results are shown in Table 4 below. Key statistics included beta coefficients, students' values, level of significance, and observed explanatory power. Analyses were done at a 95 percent level of confidence. Observed explanatory power was considered acceptable if above 0.500, high if above 0.750, and excellent if equal to 1.000 (Shenhar et al., 2002). Any observed power values below 0.500 were considered unacceptable. The student's values were considered acceptable if they were above +/- 1.96 for the two-tailed test. Any t values between -1.96 and +1.96 were considered to be outside the range of acceptance. Significance values were considered acceptable if equal to or less than 0.05 (Wamwere-Njoroge et al., 2021). Any value above 0.05 implies a lack of significance. Beta coefficients for any parameters were only accepted if all the other statistics were within acceptable limits; otherwise, the parameter was assumed to have limited capacity to explain variations of the dependent variable. All parameters demonstrated a good capacity to explain variations of all three dependent variables, as shown in the table below, except in the following circumstances:

1. The parameter X_1C (how adversely public financing challenges affect the cost of construction works in public learning institutions), which, when interacted with the

quality of construction works, failed the test. As shown in Table 4 below, whereas the beta coefficient for this variable was 0.250, the t value was -0.499, which is outside the range of acceptance; the observed power was very low at 0.076; and the level of significance, at 0.624, was far above the 0.05 acceptance limit. This result implies that public financing challenges will always affect the cost of construction works in a public learning institution, so long as the quality of the construction project is not given importance by the clients. This reaffirms the findings of Tam et al. (2006) regarding what construction project managers must do to ensure high quality.

2. The parameter X_2C (how adversely public procurement challenges affect the cost of construction works in public learning institutions), which, when interacted with the dependent variable, timeliness of construction works, failed the test. As shown in Table 4 below, its significance value was 0.176, which is far below 0.500, and the t value (1.084) was less than +1.96 of -1.96. This result implies that public procurement challenges will always affect the cost of construction works in a public learning institution, so long as the timeliness of the construction project is not given importance by the clients.
3. The parameter X_4Q (how adversely public project planning challenges affect the quality of construction works in public learning institutions), which, when interacted with the dependent variable, cost of construction works, failed the test. As shown in Table 4 below, the t statistic measured 0.547, the significance statistic stood at 0.591, and the observed explanatory power stood at 0.081. All these statistics fell outside the margin of acceptance. This result implies that public project planning challenges will always affect the quality of construction works in a public learning institution, so long as the cost of the construction project is not given importance by the clients. This implies that governments should not place undue emphasis on cost minimization if quality performance is to be guaranteed in public construction works.

Parameter Definitions

X_1C : How public financing challenges affect the cost of construction works in public learning institutions.

X_2C : How public procurement challenges affect the cost of construction works in public learning institutions.

X_3C : How public works management challenges affect the cost of construction works in public learning institutions.

X_4C : How public project planning challenges affect the cost of construction projects in public learning institutions

X_1Q : How do public financing challenges affect the quality of construction works in public learning institutions?

X_2Q : How do public procurement challenges affect the quality of construction works in public learning institutions?

X_3Q : How do public works management challenges affect the quality of construction works in public learning institutions?

X_4Q : How Public Project Planning Challenges Affect the Quality of Construction Works in Public Learning Institutions

X_1T : How public financing challenges affect the timeliness of construction works in public learning institutions

X_2T : How public procurement challenges affect the timeliness of construction works in public learning institutions

X_3T : How public works management challenges affect the timeliness of construction works in public learning institutions

X4T: How public project planning challenges affect the timeliness of construction works in public learning institutions

Table 4: Parameter Estimates Matrix

Dependent Variable	*Parameter	β	Std. Error	t	Sig.	Observed Power
Timeliness of construction works in public learning institutions	Intercept	3.140E-14	1.261E-14	2.490	.023	.651
	X1C	-2.491E-13	7.793E-14	-3.196	.005	.853
	X2C	5.066E-14	4.671E-14	1.084	.293	.176
	X3C	-2.521E-12	1.725E-13	-14.613	.000	1.000
	X4C	7.292E-13	8.559E-14	8.519	.000	1.000
	X1Q	2.472E-12	1.255E-13	19.700	.000	1.000
	X2Q	-5.115E-13	6.017E-14	-8.502	.000	1.000
	X3Q	4.161E-13	1.141E-13	3.646	.002	.930
	X4Q	1.381E-12	6.885E-14	20.052	.000	1.000
	X1T	.250	5.949E-14	4202173888968.063	.000	1.000
	X2T	.250	6.193E-14	4036847013318.321	.000	1.000
	X3T	.250	1.329E-13	1881329085437.439	.000	.
	X4T	.250	1.160E-13	2154259418552.371	.000	1.000
Quality of construction products in public learning institutions	Intercept	-7.597E-14	1.564E-14	-4.857	.000	.995
	X1C	-4.822E-14	9.664E-14	-.499	.624	.076
	X2C	-3.157E-13	5.793E-14	-5.450	.000	.999
	X3C	6.034E-13	2.139E-13	2.821	.012	.758
	X4C	-1.706E-12	1.061E-13	-16.069	.000	1.000
	X1Q	.250	1.556E-13	1606326724191.599	.000	1.000
	X2Q	.250	7.462E-14	3350350890114.771	.000	.
	X3Q	.250	1.415E-13	1766405606188.610	.000	1.000
	X4Q	.250	8.539E-14	2927843460528.750	.000	.
	X1T	3.856E-13	7.378E-14	5.227	.000	.998
	X2T	-1.141E-12	7.680E-14	-14.862	.000	1.000
	X3T	1.103E-12	1.648E-13	6.696	.000	1.000
	X4T	2.624E-12	1.439E-13	18.231	.000	1.000
Cost of construction works in public learning institutions	Intercept	-8.021E-14	4.873E-14	-1.646	.118	.342
	X1C	.250	3.011E-13	830282097672.322	.000	.
	X2C	.250	1.805E-13	1385067106831.515	.000	1.000
	X3C	.250	6.665E-13	375080832703.184	.000	1.000
	X4C	.250	3.307E-13	755916245837.035	.000	1.000
	X1Q	2.573E-12	4.849E-13	5.307	.000	.999
	X2Q	-1.005E-12	2.325E-13	-4.321	.000	.982
	X3Q	-2.757E-12	4.410E-13	-6.252	.000	1.000
	X4Q	1.455E-13	2.660E-13	.547	.591	.081
	X1T	1.606E-12	2.299E-13	6.987	.000	1.000
	X2T	5.708E-13	2.393E-13	2.385	.029	.614
	X3T	-4.557E-12	5.135E-13	-8.874	.000	1.000
	X4T	-1.916E-12	4.484E-13	-4.272	.001	.980

4.0 DISCUSSIONS

The gender distribution revealed that there was a gender disparity in favor of males in management positions in the education sector in Baringo County. Another 40 percent of the respondents were over 45 years old. This distribution was expected since most people in management positions in Kenya are senior public servants who have served for at least 15 years. The fact that over 50 percent of the respondents had been in their positions of responsibility for less than five years could imply that a lack of experience by project management teams is responsible for the unsuccessful completion of construction projects in

public learning institutions. This finding is a corroboration of opinions expressed by other workers (Bayliss et al., 2004; Anvuur and Kumaraswamy, 2007; Odeh and Battaineh, 2002; Maloney, 2002). The general educational qualifications of the respondents were quite high. Lack of education among the parties concerned, therefore, cannot be an explanation for any unsuccessful completion of the construction projects they manage or facilitate in public learning institutions.

It was found that a construction project in a public learning institution that takes a long time to complete usually costs more. Eriksson (2008) and Korczynski (1996) have argued that this positive correlation between time and cost is attributable to the fact that public construction engineers focus on short-term individual sub-optimization rather than the long-term performance of the project management team as a whole. This compromises project cost performance and results in unwarranted time overruns (Kikwasi, 2012; Muchungu, 2012). This finding demonstrates that public works management challenges adversely affect both the timeliness and cost of a construction project in a public learning institution.

It was found that quality and timeliness had a weak but statistically significant negative correlation at a 95 percent level of confidence (-0.333). The longer a construction project in a public learning institution takes to complete, the lower the quality of the works. This reaffirms the findings of several authors on the relationship between timeliness and quality in public construction projects. Both Koehn and Datta (2003) and Korczynski (1996) found that prolonged construction project durations resulted in a reduced quality of the final product. They blamed it on a lack of inclusivity during the procurement process. Writing on the same subject, Dubbois and Gadde (2002) argued that the exclusion of the contractor from the design process resulted in a divorce between design and construction works, with the consequence that projects took longer than planned and resulted in buildings of questionable quality. This confirms the hypothesis that public procurement challenges affect both timeliness and quality of works in a construction project at a public learning institution. This study, however, was conducted in only one of Kenya's 47 counties. It is recommended that a similar study be conducted on a national scale to determine the impact of these challenges nationally. Again, more research is needed to unearth the exact relationship between management experience and the successful completion of construction projects in public learning institutions in Kenya.

5.0 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Unsuccessful completion of construction works is rampant in Kenya's public learning institutions because the three most desired outcomes (high quality, minimum cost, and timeliness) are incompatible and cannot be attained concurrently. To put the quality of works above a certain level, the financing agent (NG-CDF) must forego cost minimization. The procurement team must forego cost minimization to complete the project within a certain time limit. The planning team must forego high quality to keep project costs below a certain level. In general, school construction projects that last longer than planned cost more and result in lower-quality buildings. There is a need for the Kenyan government to review the laws and regulations that govern public project financing and procurement to create greater flexibility in construction project decision-making. Specifically, the NG-CDF Act, 2015; the Public Procurement and Disposal Act; and the Public Finance Act should be reviewed to facilitate better project management. There is also a need to evaluate the same research questions using a similar multipronged approach but on a wider scale.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors harbour no conflict of interest and declare that this article is available for public use without undue hindrance.

REFERENCES

- Ambrosio-Albala, P., Upham, P., and Gale, W. (2023). Normative Expectations of Government as a Policy Actor: The Case of UK Steel Industry Decarburation. *International journal of sustainable energy*, 42,594-611.
- Andi, S., and Minato, T. (2003). Design Document Quality in the Japanese Construction Industry: Factors Influencing and Impacts on the Construction Process. *International Journal of Project Management*, 21 (7), 537–546.
- Anvuur, A., and Kumaraswamy, M. (2007). Conceptual Model of Partnering and Alliancing. *Journal of Construction Engineering and Management*, 133 (3), 225-234.
- Bayliss et al. (2004). Effective Partnering Tools in Construction: A Case Study on MTRC TKE Contract in Hong Kong. *International Journal of Project Management*, 22(3), 253-263.
- Berawi, M., Kim, A., Van Basten, N., Miraj, L., and Sari, M. (2021). Designing a Smart Integrated Work Space to Improve Building Energy Efficiency: An Indonesian Study. *International journal of construction management*, 23,410–422.
- Bresnen, M., and Marshall, N. (2000). Partnering in Construction: A Critical Review of Issues, Problems, and Dilemmas. *Construction Management and Economics*, 18(2), 229–237.
- Chan, A. P. C., and Chan, A. P. L. (2004). Key performance indicators for measuring construction success benchmarked. *An Int Journal*, vol. 11(2), pp. 2003–2022.
- Cheung, S., et al. (2003). Behavioural Aspects in Construction Partnering. *International Journal of Project Management*, 21(5), 333–343.
- Chan, D. et al. (1999). Critical success factors for different project objectives. *Journal of Construction Engineering and Management*, 125 (3), 142-150.
- Crawley, D. I., and Aho. (1999). Building Environmental Assessment Methods: Applications and Development Trends. *Building Research & Information*, 27 (4/5), 300–308.
- De Luca, A., Chan, L., and Gharehbaghi, K. (2021). Sustainable Utilization of Recycled Aggregates: Robust Construction and Demolition Waste Reduction Strategies. *International Journal of Building Pathology Adaptations*, 39, 666–682.
- Department of Education (DOE) (2009). *School funding and management in South Africa: Findings from the School Survey* Department of Education, Republic of South Africa. Pretoria, South Africa.
- Dimitriou, S., Kyprianou, I., Papanicolas, C., and Serghides, D. (2020). A New Approach to Refurbishment of Office Buildings: From Standard to Alternative Nearly Zero Energy Buildings. *International journal of sustainable energy*, 39, 761–778
- Dubois, A., and L. E. Gadde (2002). The Construction Industry as a Loosely Coupled System: Implications for Productivity and Innovation. *Construction Management and Economics*, 20(7), 621-632.
- Eriksson, P. E. (2007). Efficient Governance of Construction Projects through Cooperative Procurement Procedures. *Business Administration and Management*. Lulea University of Technology.
- Eriksson, P.E., and A. Laan (2007). Procurement Effects on Trust and Control in Client-Contractor Relationships. *Eng, Const, and Architectural Mgt*, 14(4), 387–399.
- Eriksson, P. E. (2008). Procurement Effects on Coopetition in Client-Contractor Relationships. *Journal of Construction Engineering and Management*, 134 (2), 103–111.

- Eriksson, P.E., and Westerberg (2007), Modeling Procurement Effects on Cooperation. *Business Administration and Management*. Lulea University of Technology.
- Government of Kenya (GoK) (2012). The Kenya Universities Act, 2012 Government Printing Press, Nairobi.
- Government of Kenya (GoK) (2013). The Kenya TVET Act No. 29 of 2013. Government Printing Press, Nairobi.
- Government of Kenya (GoK) (2015). The Kenya NG-CDF Act No. 30 of 2015. Government Printing Press, Nairobi.
- Gwayo et al. (2014). A Critical Analysis of the Causes of Project Management Failures in Kenya. *International Journal of Soft Computing and Engineering*, 4(1), 64–69.
- Hoskisson, R.E. et al. (1999). Theory and Research in Strategic Management. *Journal of Management*, vol. 25, No 3.
- John, O., and O. Sam. (2009). An overview of the poultry sector and the status of Highly Pathogenic Avian Influenza (HPAI) in Kenya *background paper*.
- Kikwasi, G. J. (2012). Causes and Effects of Delays and Disruptions in Construction Projects in Tanzania. *Aust J Const Economics and Building, Conference Series*, 1(2): 52–59.
- Koehn, E., and N. Datta (2003). Quality, Environmental, and Health and Safety Management Systems for Construction Engineering. *J Const Eng and Mgt*, 129(5), 562–569.
- Korczyński, M. (1996), 'The Low-Trust Route to Economic Development: Inter-Firm Relations in the UK Engineering Construction Industry in the 1980s and 1990s. *Journal of Management Studies*, 33(6), 787-808.
- Latham, M. (1994). Constructing the team: Joint review of procurement and contractual arrangements in the United Kingdom. *Design, drawing, and print services*.
- Maloney, W. (2002). Construction Product/Service and Customer Satisfaction. *Construction Engineering and Management*, 128(6), 522–529.
- Muchungu, P. K. (2012). The contribution of human factors to the performance of construction projects in Kenya. Unpublished PhD thesis. University of Nairobi.
- Murray, M.D. et al. (2002). Construction Procurement Systems: Don't Forget Murphy's Law. Paper submitted at the International Symposium of the Working Committee, CIB W92 (Procurement Systems).
- Odeh, A., and H. Battaineh. (2002). Causes of Construction Delays: Traditional Contracts. *International Journal of Project Management*, 20 (1), 67–73.
- Reichstein, T. et al. (2005). Last among equals: a comparison of innovation in construction, services, and manufacturing in the UK. *Construction mgt and economics*, 23, 631-644.
- Swan, W., and M. Khalfan (2007). Mutual Objective Setting for Partnering Projects in the Public Sector. *Engineering, Construction, and Architectural Mgt*, 4(2), 119–130.
- Tam, C. M. (2000). Design and Build on a Complicated Redevelopment Project in Hong Kong: The Happy Valley Racecourse Redevelopment. *Int J Project Mgt*, 18(2), 125-129.
- Tam, V. et al. (2006). Critical factors for environmental performance assessment (EPA) in the Hong Kong construction industry. *Const mgt and economics*, 24 (11), 1113–1123.
- Tam, V., and C.M. Tam. (2008). Waste Reduction through Incentives: A Case Study. *Building Research and Information*, 36 (1), 37–43.
- Saisi, E.A. et al. (2015). Financial Factors Influencing Successful Completion of Construction Projects in Public Universities: A Case of Egerton University, Kenya.
- Shenhar, A. J. et al. (2002). Refining the Search for Project Success Factors: A Multivariate, Typological Approach. *Research and Development Mgt* 32, 2. Blackwell Publishers.
- Pokhariyal, G. P. (2019). Importance of Moderating and Intervening Variables, or the Relationship Between Independent and Dependent Variables. *International Journal of Statistics and Applied Mathematics*, 4(5):01-04.

- Talukhaba, A.A. (1999). An Investigation into the Factors Causing Construction Project Delays in Kenya. A Case Study of High-rise Building Projects in Nairobi. *Unpublished PhD. Thesis. University of Nairobi.*
- Wamwere-Njoroge et al. (2021) Feed the Future Accelerated Value Chain Development (AVCD) Program: Effect of COVID-19 on Livestock Value Chain Actors and Food Systems in Northern Kenya, 2021, *Nairobi, Kenya. International Livestock Research Institute.*